

Towards the next generation of high-performance Li-Ion battery cells

WORK PACKAGE 9 (WP9)

D9.1 Dissemination and communication plan

Lead Contractor: SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE)

Author: Mariana Fernández

This document is the NEXTCELL project Dissemination and Communication Plan (contract no. 101069910) corresponding to D9.1 (M6) led by SIE.

Project acronym	NEXTCELL	Start duration	JANUARY 2023 (48 months)
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-02		
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA		
Contact persons	Mariana Fernández, Sustainable Innovations, Communications Manager Servais Ouenou, FEV France, Administrative Coordinator Thorsten Schnorbus, FEV GmbH, Technical Coordinator		
Website	www.nextcell.eu		

Deliverable details			
Number	D9.1		
Title	Dissemination and Communication Plan		
Work Package	9		
Dissemination level	Public	Nature	PU - Public
Due date (M)	June 30,2023	Submission date (M)	June 30,2023
Deliverable responsible	Mariana Fernández	Contact Person	marianafernandez@sustainableinnovations.eu

Deliverable contributors			
Deliverable leader	Mariana Fernández		
Contributing authors	Miguel Gallardo, Sustainable Innovations (SIE) Antonio Barona, CEO Sustainable Innovations (SIE)		
Reviewers	Emmanuel Lorenzo (INEGI). André Oliveira (Nanomakers)		
Final review and quality approval	Pierre Gaudillat	Contact Person	gaudillat@fev.com

Deliverable history	
V0.1	First draft version
V0.2	Implement changes as per events attended by FEV and Polito
V0.3	Changes requested by INEGI & figures social media & website implemented

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

1. Acronyms and abbreviations

OS Open science

CINEA	European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
KER	Key Exploitable Result
HE	Horizon Europe
DC	Dissemination and Communication
SIE	Sustainable innovations
M	Month
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
R&I	Research and Innovation
RM	Raw Materials
AM	Active Materials
CMEM	Cell manufacturing & equipment manufacturers
BPS	Battery Packs & Systems
OEM	Application & Integration
RSL	Recycling / Second Life
SC	Scientific community
PM	Policymakers
STC	Standardisation Technical Committees
GP	General Public
TM	Trade Media

2. Executive summary

Currently marketed cells are composed of liquid (electrolyte) and solid (electrodes, separators, etc.) materials. For 48 months, NEXTCELL, formed by 17 partners from 10 different European countries, will work to obtain the next generation of high-performance Li-Ion battery cells by developing and validating a ground-breaking gellified cell concept, integrating several innovations at the material level for each of the main cell components: the gellification of the electrodes and the separator, in combination with a high voltage-stable gel electrolyte. As a result, the cells prototyped in the project will offer a high energy density allowing excellent performance in high power and high voltage applications.

NEXTCELL will not only provide the European market with state-of-the-art cells but will also address three key aspects that currently hinder further market penetration of Li-Ion battery technology, such as costs, safety, and sustainability.

In this sense, the technology developed by NEXTCELL will optimise, first, the manufacturing processes, reducing the capital and operating costs of future gigafactories, by avoiding the evaporation of solvents and the electrolyte filling step. Secondly, the project will produce intrinsically safe cells, avoiding the presence of low-boiling point components in the electrodes and the separator. Finally, a reduction of around 50% in energy consumption will be guaranteed.

3. Introduction

This document describes the Dissemination and Communication Plan to be adopted by the NEXTCELL project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to appropriate target communities.

3.1 Context of WP9

The main aim of WP9 is to coordinate the project consortium in the performance of dissemination, communications, and exploitation activities, including IP management. Following the OS approach of the project partners will maximise the openness of results and the interaction with sectoral stakeholders in a balanced way with IP protection measures established where necessary to ensure the proper exploitation of project KERs.

3.2 Objectives of task 9.1

A detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C) and publication report has been produced by SIE at the beginning of the project (M6) and will be updated at the end of each reporting period, based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2 and in collaboration with all the consortium partners. It will outline the project's audiences, key messages, and communication channels for the dissemination, including roles and responsibilities. The different updates of the plan will offer the monitoring of the different dissemination and communications activities carried out by all partners, evaluated against its KPIs.

4. Objectives

In order to deliver and achieve the outcomes and impacts of the project, NEXTCELL has set a specific plan for the dissemination, usage, and valorisation of research and innovation results. This document includes outreach efforts to inform the public about the utilisation of European funds for R&I projects, social issues, the results of a sustainable and cutting-edge cell manufacturing sector in the EU. Thus, improving the communication between science, business, and society. WP9, "Dissemination, exploitation, and communication," will take the lead on these efforts, liaising with the other partners to ensure the greatest impact is made, and delivering a comprehensive Dissemination and communication Plan by M6. Here is a brief explanation of the main components of this proposal.

5. Target audiences

A sizable list of stakeholders has been initially established by NETXCELL for whom the distribution and communication tools and materials will be intended. Although the vehicle manufacturing sector is an established industry, the electric vehicle one, the associated deployment of the cell manufacturing ecosystem in Europe, as well as the stationary sector are not. This, which justifies the value chain strategy used in the project, which is typical of fast expanding industries. In this sense, the following table lists the key players in the value chain along with the key findings that will be shared with them throughout the project.

Table 1. Target groups and contents

Targeted results/content	Targeted groups
Optimised cell component materials / New 3b gen components for high-power/energy density	Raw Materials (RM), Active Materials (AM), Cell manufacturing & equipment manufacturers (CMEM), Scientific Community (SC), Policy Makers (PM), Standardisation Technical Committees (STC), General Public (GP)
Gellified cell concept and design / New 3b gen which are better, safer, greener, prepared for easy recycling and large-scale manufacturing	CMEM, Battery Packs & Systems (BPS), Application & Integration (OEM), Recycling / Second Life (RSL), AM, PM, STC, GP
Multi-scale and multi-physics modelling and simulation tools / Accelerated R&D cell design, reducing time to market of innovations and increasing flexibility and quality	CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, PM, STC, GP
Fine-tuned characterisation techniques / Increased knowledge on gellified concept	CMEM, SC, PM, STC, GP
Recycling process / Enabling industrial closed loop, upcycling of materials and reduced costs and environmental impacts	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, RSL, PM, STC, SC, GP
Knowledge, reproducibility, etc.	SC

Standardisation, actualisation, etc.	public roadmaps	PM, STC
EC funds, R&I efforts to enable affordable electric mobility.		GP, TM
Europe at the forefront of the battery industry, leading gigafactory construction: employment, reducing costs, boosting local and regional economy, etc.		GP, TM

NEXTCELL has identified a significant list of target groups to which the dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed to, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1 summarises how the different stakeholder groups will be benefited from the project's results, The dissemination and communication strategy will conduct a thorough value chain analysis to better understand the influence and stakeholder interests, and to better adjust the key messages to deliver and how to do so, increasing the likelihood that the project's findings will be disseminated and used.

NEXTCELL consortium members have preliminary identified a list of key associations and organisations that will allow to enhance the project's results dissemination through mutual collaboration: [LiPLANET](#) (Network of battery cell Pilot Lines in Europe), [European Battery Alliance](#), [EMIRI](#), [ALISTORE](#), [EMMC](#) (European Materials Modelling Council), [BEPA](#) - BATT4EU Partnership, [BATTERY 2030+](#), [European Digital SME Alliance](#), and [ERMA](#) (European Raw Materials Alliance).

Consortium partners are a good reflection of the European battery value chain, including research centers, manufacturers, producers, and academia. Nevertheless, NEXTCELL's intention is to widen its collaboration with other relevant actors from the industry.

Likewise, similar European and international projects have been identified to seek for synergies: [3beLiEVe](#), [ASTRABAT](#), [BatWoman](#), [COFBAT H2o2o](#), [DEFACTO](#), [eCAIMAN](#), [greenSPEED](#), [HIFI ELEMENTS](#), [HIGHSPIN](#), [HYDRA](#), [InteliLiGent](#), [NoVOC](#), [MAESTRI](#), [SIGNE](#), and [SPIDER](#). NEXTCELL has created a dedicated section on its [website](#), so stakeholders can easily access all their information.

Finally, a set of trade media contacts was listed, including the most relevant magazines: [Autobuild](#), [Autofacil](#), [Automotive news](#), [Autopista](#), [Autovolt](#), [Batteries and energy stories news](#), [Batteries International](#), [Battery Power Magazine](#), [Car and driver](#), [Charged electrical vehicles magazine](#), [Clicacoches.com](#), [Electrek](#), [Electric and hybrid world](#), [Electric cars report](#), [Electric Hybrid vehicles magazine](#), [Electrical India](#), [Energy Magazine Australia](#), [EV Magazine](#), [Inside EVS](#), [KM 77](#), [Motor 16](#), [Motor authority](#), [Motortrend](#). Also, project partners are expected to generate at least 10 peer review articles targeting Journals like [Journal of Cleaner Production](#), [Resources, Conservation and Recycling](#), and [International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment](#), as well as the open access site from the EC [Open Research Europe](#).

6. Key messages

The NEXTCELL project will produce a significant amount of knowledge across seven technical WPs, sparking interest across the value chain for cell batteries as well as the vehicle and stationary industries. The outputs and messages from produced WPs, as well as the suitable instruments and channels for distribution, must be

identified. The essential messages from each WP are displayed in Table 2 below. Additionally, the primary target group(s) and distribution channels are established. The consortium group will keep spreading information about its overall goals and partnership engagement in anticipated activities. This includes private business meetings, presentations to possible clients, and scientific materials, milestones, etc.

Table 2. Key messages

WP	Key message	Target group / Key channels
Requirement specification in predefined Use Cases	Key methodology to optimise and accelerate the research and development process of new energy storage technologies.	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC
Development of the raw material and definition of the continuous solventless production of gellified electrodes and separator.	Simplified gellified cell manufacturing process, removing the most energy intensive step (drying and recovery of solvent), and thus reducing CO ₂	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC
Cell design and manufacture at pouch cell level.	Optimisation of manufacturing processes, reducing capital and operating costs of future gigafactories, by avoiding the evaporation of solvents and the electrolyte filling step.	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Electrochemical characterisation, and thermal, ageing and safety tests.	Intrinsically safe cells, avoiding the presence of low-boiling point components in the electrodes and the separator.	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Large Gellified cell prototyping	Excellent performance in high capacity and high voltage applications.	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Modelling the gellified cell concept	Development and use of physical-chemical models. Mathematical modelling, experimentation, and prototyping	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Sustainable production and material recovery	Reduction of around 50% in energy consumption.	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM

7. Tools and channels

The actions carried out by NEXTCELL and its results will be disseminated and communicated using a variety of methods and means. The Dissemination Plan will be more effective since each instrument and channel will be used effectively to speak to various target groups at various stages of the project execution. Table 3 shows the connections between the target audiences, the tools and channels, and the anticipated outcomes.

Table 3: Tools and channels

Channels	Tools	Target group	Expected impacts
Printed materials	Brochure	All target groups	Create awareness about the project goals and expected impacts
	Leaflet		
	Poster		
	Roll up		
Online	Website	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM	Keep the audience engaged on the project objectives and outcomes, as well as on achievements, and news.
	Newsletters	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM	
	Social media	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM	
Publications	Scientific papers	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Guarantee knowledge transfer
	Articles	All target groups	Generate interest in the cell battery production and the state-of-the-art technologies developed by NEXTCELL
	Press releases	TM	Regularly inform trade media on the project outcomes and how this impact positively in European lives in

			terms of employment, technology development, improvement of environmental footprint, etc
Events organised by NEXTCELL	Workshops Webinars	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Create awareness about the project goals and expected impacts
Events attended by NEXTCELL	Conferences Tradeshows	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Keep the audience engaged on the project objectives and outcomes, as well as on achievements, and news.

The project website, articles written for both a lay and technical readership, press releases, e-newsletters, scientific papers and booklets, social media presence, and attendance at workshops and conferences are some of the methods and channels proposed to be employed in this plan.

The dissemination plan described in section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement serves as the foundation for all efforts involving communication with stakeholders outside the project consortium. The goal of journal articles is largely to inform the academic and scientific communities of current discoveries. To spread new pertinent solutions to more potential end consumers, the project will also publish in key trade publications and magazines. The same audience is targeted for project presentations at technical conferences.

The European logo will be displayed along with the disclaimer that the project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe initiative in all dissemination efforts and publications, including the project website. The European emblem will be given the proper prominence when shown alongside a logo.

7.1 Project identity

In order to build a visual brand, a distinctive project identity has been created. It provides a set of templates that will make it easier to gain reputation as the project progresses. This involves developing the project's logo and the related style guide. Additional communication materials have been developed and made available on the project [website](#). This includes the project roll up, poster, factsheet, brochure, and presentation.

Image 1 NEXTCELL brand guidelines

Logo Color Versions

Main Brand Colors

	PANTONE 2224 C CMYK 36 0 31 57 RGB 0 105 128 #006680		PANTONE 5523 C CMYK 22 19 2 RGB 162 207 208 #A6C7D0		PANTONE 7621 C CMYK 0 98 91 30 RGB 171 35 40 #AB232B
--	--	--	---	--	--

Secondary Colors

	PANTONE 143 C CMYK 0 32 87 0 RGB 241 180 52 #F0A434		PANTONE Cool Gray 1 C CMYK 4 2 4 8 RGB 207 207 204 #D0D0C6
--	---	--	--

Brand & Web Font (Google Fonts)

Encode Sans
 SemiExpanded SemiBold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 - !@? * ^ ~ []

Encode Sans
 SemiExpanded Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 - !@? * ^ ~ []

Titulares
Subtitulares

Que nī dolentum, editame dolese sim quae labor
 sequist iumquo velluptur re consequo omnia
 nem nem explaccus simolup taquiase captatur,
 solupit vero beatiat empellia eossimus et maxirpe
 diaecatis et eat.

Maximolube plabone a cuptatus, et il idera cora
 dudi aut erit harum quaepris mod ut harchil int ma
 doluptae nam saquo volupiat.

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

@nextcellproject
 www.nextcell.eu

7.2 Project website

The NEXTCELL project website, has been created and it will be continuously updated to be appealing for visitors. It was made available on M2 of the project life and serve as main repository of the project information and outcomes.

For the time being, it has four main sections:

1. **About.** This tab contains information on the project goals, approach, and implementation. It also counts on NEXTCELL's partners logos and description, as well as the most relevant related initiatives and associations.
2. **Downloads.** NEXTCELL has made available the main resources till today: [brochure](#), [poster](#), [factsheet](#), [presentation](#), [logo](#) and [roll up](#). There, visitors can also find the [first press release](#) and [newsletter](#) issued.
3. **News.** In this section, the project will inform stakeholders about the latest updates on the project progress, interviews, and events at where partners will disseminate NEXTCELL.
4. **Contact.** Whoever might be interested in reaching out NEXTCELL, here they can simply fill out the form and contact the consortia.

7.3 Social media

To ensure greater diffusion to various age groups and target audiences, NEXTCELL will have a social media presence on Twitter and LinkedIn. Social media should be utilised to promote project updates and, most significantly, to increase website traffic.

In order to broaden reach, NEXTCELL-related content has been posted often starting in M1 on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#). When the project has video content, a YouTube channel will also be made available.

In order to create an audience for the project results, the social media accounts will distribute updates about the project scope and promote events where NEXTCELL will be showcased throughout the first phase of the project.

Online media platforms will be supervised to gather data on the metrics, sources, content kinds, and people or organisations who support or spread project messaging. This information will enable communication to be targeted and optimised for maximum reach of news or results. The final dissemination report and interim reports will both include these findings. SIE will be responsible for the social media profiles, assisted by partners.

Consortium members will follow and participate as much as they can in the project's social media platforms. The partners will frequently share posts on their own corporate websites and social media platforms. SIE can advise them on the most effective ways to do so if they require support.

Table 4 Milestones suitable to be communicated.

Milestone	WP	Lead partner	Date
Project Kick off meeting	WP1	FEV	M1
Project website running	WP9	SIE	M2
Dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy provided	WP9	SIE	M6
Cell requirements and testing protocols specified	WP2	CRF	M9
Decision point on whether the latest iteration of newly developed materials should be scaled-up (ca. 50kg) and deliver to WP4 partners, or the iterative process should continue.	WP3	SOLVAY	M18
Preliminary environmental performance assessment completed	WP8	INEGI	M18
Demonstration of functional simulation toolchain for performance, aging, and safety, waiting for final calibration and validation data	WP7	CEA	M24
GEN1 materials of WP3 electrochemically tested	WP5	POLITO	M30
Assembly of prototypes of ~500 mAh pouch cells using optimised materials	WP4	CICE	M36
Large prototype cells manufactured	WP6	ABEE	M40

7.4 Printed material

To be distributed at conferences, exhibitions, and other events, as well as to partner networks, a poster, a roll-up, a factsheet, and a brochure have been created. General information regarding the research activities, participants, and anticipated outcomes is included in the initial project poster and brochure version. Later in the project life, other materials could be created to publicise findings.

Image 2 NEXTCELL brochure

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

in nextcell

@nextcellproject
www.nextcell.eu

NEXTCELL'S

overarching goal is to **provide a new Li-Ion cell generation for both high capacity and high voltage** applications by developing and validating a **ground-breaking gellified cell concept**, integrating several innovations at the material level for each of the main cell components: the gellification of the electrodes and the separator in combination with a high voltage-stable gel electrolyte will allow the development of the full gel cell concept.

GELLIFIED CELL CONCEPT

High energy density.

Excellent performance in high capacity and high voltage applications.

Physical and mathematical models.

Key methodology to optimise and accelerate the research and development process of new energy storage technologies.

Sustainable.

Optimisation of manufacturing processes, reducing capital and operating costs of future gigafactories, by avoiding the evaporation of solvents and the electrolyte filling step.

Cheaper.

Reduction of around 50% in energy consumption.

Safer.

Intrinsically safe cells, avoiding the presence of low-boiling point components in the electrodes and the separator.

Image 3 NEXTCELL poster

GELLIFIED CELL CONCEPT

- **High energy density.**
Excellent performance in high capacity and high voltage applications.
- **Physical and mathematical models.**
Key methodology to optimise and accelerate the research and development process of new energy storage technologies.
- **Sustainable.**
Optimisation of manufacturing processes, reducing capital and operating costs of future gigafactories, by avoiding the evaporation of solvents and the electrolyte filling step.
- **Cheaper.**
Reduction of around 50% in energy consumption.
- **Safer.**
Intrinsically safe cells, avoiding the presence of low-boiling point components in the electrodes and the separator.

NEXTCELL'S

overarching goal is to provide a new Li-Ion cell generation for both high capacity and high voltage applications by developing and validating a ground-breaking gellified cell concept, integrating several innovations at the material level for each of the main cell components: the gellification of the electrodes and the separator in combination with a high voltage-stable gel electrolyte will allow the development of the full gel cell concept.

PARTNERS

 Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

 @nextcellproject
www.nextcell.eu

Image 4 NEXTCELL factsheet

50%
energy consumption reduction

> 70%
recycling efficiency

> 90%
lithium recovery

 Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

 @nextcellproject
www.nextcell.eu

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

 @nextcellproject
www.nextcell.eu

7.5 Newsletters and press releases

Every six months, electronic newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other NEXTCELL-related information will be created. These newsletters will be sent to stakeholders and partner networks as well as uploaded on the project website.

Additionally, project updates could be included in the partners' own newsletters, which are sent electronically to the contacts they have within the relevant industries.

Press releases will be released to announce noteworthy project advancements as they happen. With the support of the project partners, they will be written in English and distributed to the national media and the European press.

7.6 Peer-reviewed articles

The technical and academic partners will create at least 10 scientific papers, bringing additional benefits like greater transparency in the research process, better opportunities for new scientific collaborations, and increased efficiencies in research. The project's findings will be disseminated both internationally in international journals like [Journal of Materials Chemistry](#) or [Journal of Power Sources](#), as well as nationally, primarily in the Member States where the partners are based. Open Research Europe is an open access, free of cost alternative as well for partners.

Likewise, the project website will compile all publications and make them available for free download.

7.7 Conferences and events

To meet target audiences, other stakeholders, public authorities, and the scientific community, project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, and workshops. They will also spread the word about the project's goals and outcomes. Access to target audiences at the local, national, European, and worldwide levels will be made possible by these events.

The following conferences and trade shows have been pointed out as being of interest to the NEXTCELL project:

- [Therminic](#). September 2023
- [Thermal management for EV/EHV](#). November 2023
- [Future Battery Forum](#). November 2023
- [International Motor Show](#). October 2023
- [Electric & hybrid vehicle technology expo](#). May 2023
- [Vehicle Electrification Expo](#). June 2023
- [Automotive Testing Expo](#). June 2023
- [Green Vehicle Expo](#). June 2023
- [Life Cycle Innovation Conference](#). August 2024
- [5th International Conference on Battery and Fuel Cell Technology](#). October 2023
- [International Electric Vehicle Symposium and Exhibition](#). June 2023
- [E MOVE 360° EUROPE](#). October 2023
- [31 & 32 LCE Conference](#). June 2024 & 2025
- [ICBSC 2024](#).

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

- [Battery Innovation Days](#). November 2023

In order to ensure that the project is present at events for dissemination, this list of events will be updated often in partnership with the consortia.

Along with attending conferences and trade shows, NEXTCELL will collaborate with other initiatives under the same call to host at least two workshops by the end of the project to address standardisation and policies, as well as four other webinars to raise awareness on the different project propositions.

8. Indicators and targets

The accomplishment of particular targets for various indicators will serve as a gauge for how well the Dissemination and Communication Plan is being implemented.

Table 5 Indicators and targets

Tools and channels	Indicator	Target number	Information source
Brochure Poster Factsheet	Number of copies distributed	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders
Website	Number of visits	Visits per year: <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics
Social media (Twitter, LinkedIn)	Number of followers Number of impressions Engagement rate	Twitter; (a) Followers: < 100 poor; 100 – 200 good; > 200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn; (a) Followers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2- 3%	Social media analytics

Videos	Number of views Audience in conferences /trade shows	At least 2 in the project. Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	YouTube, website and social media analytics Attendance to booth /conference
Newsletters	Number of subscribers Number of opens Visits from website / social media	At least one each six months. Subscribers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >300 excellent Opens: <15% poor; 15% – 17% good; >17% excellent	Mailchimp (newsletter service), Website and social media analytics
Press releases	Number of media stakeholders addressed Number of views on website and social media	At least 4. 100 media sources / journalists reached Number of views: < 40 = poor; 40-60 = good; >60 = excellent	Recording of e- mails sent, Website and social media analytics
Scientific publications	Number of views/ downloads	10 publications	Link to site where posted or PDF version of article
Workshops	Number of attendees	1 standardisation + 1 policy feedback workshop. Number of attendees each: <15 = poor; 15-25 = good; >25 = excellent	Registration list
Webinars	Number of attendees	4 webinars. Number of attendees: <25 = poor; 25-45 = good; >45 = excellent	Registration list /webinar platform analytics

Conferences Trade fairs	Number of conferences and trade fairs attended. Number of exhibitors and participants	Attend conferences	24	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information
----------------------------	--	--------------------	----	--

9. Levels of dissemination

The geographic levels at which the main target groups operate will affect the communication methods and media used.

9.1 European Level – European Commission

The results of the project will be reported to the EC on a regular basis (mid-term review, minutes of periodic meetings, updates to this document) so that it can make any necessary changes to the relevant regulations and suggest collaborating with other projects that are already in progress on dissemination efforts.

9.2 International Level – Industry, Scientific community

The outcomes will be communicated to the pertinent international organisations. Scientific knowledge can be converted into useful information, regulations, and guidelines. Electronic resources will be distributed by direct mailing to specified organisations and stakeholders in order to increase public awareness.

For the transmission of knowledge at both the research and industrial levels, technical journals, conferences, and workshops at both the national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be utilised.

10. Methodology

To make sure that the NEXTCELL outcomes are effectively and efficiently conveyed to the project partners, stakeholders, and wider audiences, the following internal and external communication activities will be carried out throughout the project's duration and afterward.

10.1 Internal Communication

To effectively share information and guarantee that the deliverables are met, effective internal communication is essential. Therefore, to exchange project information, update progress, and share outcomes, frequent meetings and conference calls will be held. Two times a year, consortium and technical meetings will be held, and WP collaboration will be facilitated through the use of Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing tools.

Apart from individual emails, taking advantage of the project monthly conference call, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and expedite a content curating process. As a result, the partners will be

better able to communicate and report on the project while also adopting a more methodical and focused approach. Each NEXTCELL consortium partner will send a representative to this meeting.

FEV has also set up a Microsoft SharePoint space, which will host the project materials for internal use, including regular updates on the project development, meeting documents (agenda, minutes, and presentations), and project reports. This will help partners communicate effectively with one another.

A login name and password will be required to access this exclusive area.

10.2 External Communication

The consortium will make every effort to spread the word about its activities through the media, journals, conference presentations, trade shows, workshops, the Commission, and industry associations. The project's findings will be published in reports, academic publications, and articles. To encourage scientific collaboration, all public communications and scientific publications shall be made open access.

The partners will send SIE the text whenever a translation is required, and SIE will take care of modifying the design.

11. Timeline

As the project has different development phases, the communication focus would be different across each of them.

11.1 Phase 1. Awareness phase

In this phase, NEXTCELL will prioritise the generation of a community of interested stakeholders and of suitable channels. It will comprise from months 1 to 12.

11.2 Phase 2. Scientific cooperation phase

This second phase will consist of knowledge management for the cooperation of NEXTCELL with similar projects and initiatives and ensuring the availability of research outputs to targeted audience. It will start in M6 and will last for the project duration.

11.3 Phase 3. Exploitation-focused phase

This phase will cover the support to the actual exploitation of project results via marketing towards end users (commercial results) or workshops and roadmaps (non-commercial results) and will comprise the final stages of the project (M24-M48).

12. Activities M1-M6

12.1 Project identity and materials

During the initial stage of the project, NEXTCELL's visual identity was developed. It contained the project's logo and the brand guidelines (typography, colours). A project presentation, a roll-up, a poster, and a variety of other communication tools were also created. The partners were provided with a template for the deliverables, a Word document template, and a PowerPoint template.

As soon as the website was online, the first brochure, poster, factsheet, roll-up, and project presentation were uploaded:

Image 5 Word template

Title 1

Title 2

Subtitle 1

Text 1: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

- Nunc eu libero a diam aliquet accumsan in auctor sapien.
- Duis malesuada nulla laoreet ligula imperdiet, ac imperdiet odio eleifend.
- Vivamus iaculis purus vel ipsum commodo, nec blandit nibh consequat.
- Praesent vitae odio id lorem tristique cursus.

12.2 Press releases

A press release was launched at the beginning of the project. It was sent to more than 200 local and trade media by SIE and several consortium partners.

Image 6 NEXTCELL's first press release

The NEXTCELL project kicks off to obtain the next generation of high-performance Li-Ion battery cells

- **NEXTCELL is a project financed with almost €8 million by the European Union under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe aiming to provide a new Li-Ion battery cell generation for both high capacity and high voltage applications**
- **The initiative is supported by a multidisciplinary consortium of 17 partners comprising research centres, universities, consultancy companies, material suppliers, and cell manufacturers from 10 European countries.**

Aachen (Germany), January 10. NEXTCELL, a project financed by the European Union (EU) under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe aiming to provide a new Li-Ion battery cell generation for both high capacity and high voltage applications, has just kicked off with a meeting held in Aachen (Germany).

Currently marketed cells are composed of liquid (electrolyte) and solid (electrodes, separators, etc.) materials. For 40 months, NEXTCELL, formed by 17 partners from 10 different European countries, will work to obtain the next generation of high-performance Li-Ion battery cells by developing and validating a ground-breaking gelified cell concept, integrating several innovations at the material level for each of the main cell components: the gelification of the electrodes and the separator, in combination with a high voltage-stable gel electrolyte. As a result, the cells prototyped in the project will offer a high energy density allowing excellent performance in high power and high voltage applications.

NEXTCELL will not only provide the European market with state-of-the-art cells but will also address three key aspects that currently hinder further market penetration of Li-Ion battery technology, such as costs, safety, and sustainability.

In this sense, the technology developed by NEXTCELL will optimise, first, the manufacturing processes, reducing the capital and operating costs of future gigafactories, by avoiding the evaporation of solvents and the electrolyte filling step. Secondly, the project will produce intrinsically safe cells, avoiding the presence of low-boiling point components in the electrodes and the separator. Finally, a reduction of around 50% in energy consumption will be guaranteed.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Led by FEV Europe, NEXTCELL is formed by ABBE Solvay, Nanomakers, Universitat Politècnica de València, Politecnico di Torino, Sintef, Inegi, CIC energisUNE, the French Commission for Atomic Energy and Renewable Energies (CEA), Varta Innovation, FIAT Research Centre (CRF), Nanocyl, Univerza v Ljubljani, Sustainable Innovations, Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

The total impacts for this type of communications reached 23 outlets in total, including media, consortium partners and related projects portals, as shown in Annex 1.

12.3 Website

The website www.nextcell.eu was launched on M2 with essential information of the project and will be updated constantly with progress and news from the project and partners.

Apart from the sections mentioned aboved, regarding the News section, 4 posts about the project scope, and interviews have been uploaded:

<https://nextcell.eu/archivos/118199>

<https://nextcell.eu/archivos/118491>

<https://nextcell.eu/archivos/118493>

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

[in nextcell](https://www.nextcell.eu)

[@nextcellproject](https://twitter.com/nextcellproject)
www.nextcell.eu

<https://nextcell.eu/archivos/118496>

Image 7 NEXTCELL's website analytics

12.4 Social media

The LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nextcell/> and the Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/NEXTCELLproject> were created and updated with content on a regular basis since the project's kick off.

During this period, 23 publications were shared, reaching out up to 245 followers, and our publications got a total of 19,868 impressions on LinkedIn, as of June 16.

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

www.nextcell.eu

Image 8 NEXTCELL's Twitter account

← **NEXTCELL**
50 Tweets

The profile card features a circular profile picture with the NEXTCELL logo, a large banner image of the logo on a textured surface, and interaction buttons for more options, direct message, retweet, and a 'Following' button.

NEXTCELL
@NEXTCELLproject Follows you

Towards the next generation of high-performance li-ion battery cells. Horizon Europe 101069910

📍 Aachen, North Rhine-Westphalia 🌐 nextcell.eu 📅 Joined November 2022

258 Following 85 Followers

👤 Followed by FASTESTproject, BRING vzw, and 52 others you follow

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

 nextcell

 @nextcellproject
www.nextcell.eu

Image 9 NEXTCELL's LinkedIn account

12.5 Newsletter

In M3, the first Newsletter was released as shown in Image 10.

Image 10 NEXTCELL's first newsletter

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

nextcell

@nextcellproject
www.nextcell.eu

Towards the next generation of high-performance Li-Ion battery cells

NEXTCELL project kick-off took place in Aachen (Germany) on January 25 and 26.

NEXTCELL, a project financed by the European Union (EU) under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe willing to provide a new Li-Ion battery cell generation for both high capacity and high voltage applications, has just kicked off with a meeting held in Aachen (Germany).

Currently marketed cells are composed of liquid (electrolyte) and solid (electrodes, separators, etc.) materials. For 48 months, NEXTCELL, formed by 17 partners from 10 different European countries, will work to obtain the next generation of high-performance Li-Ion battery cells by developing and validating a ground-breaking gellified cell concept, integrating several innovations at the material level for each of the main cell components: the gellification of the electrodes and the separator, in combination with a high voltage-stable gel electrolyte. As a result, the cells prototyped in the project will offer a high energy density allowing excellent performance in high power and high voltage applications.

[Read More](#)

OBJECTIVES

NEXTCELL will not only provide the European market with state-of-the-art cells but will also address three key aspects that currently hinder further market penetration of Li-Ion battery technology, such as costs, safety, and sustainability.

High energy density. Excellent performance in high capacity and high voltage applications

Physical and mathematical models. Key methodology to optimise and accelerate the research and development process of new energy storage technologies.

Sustainable. Optimisation of manufacturing processes, reducing capital and operating costs of future gigafactories, by avoiding the evaporation of solvents and the electrolyte filling step.

Cheaper. Reduction of around 50% in energy consumption.

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

[in nextcell](#)

[@nextcellproject](#)
www.nextcell.eu

12.6 Events attended

During M1-M6 of the project, NEXTCELL has been disseminated to external audiences at different events and conferences that we list below:

1. [Alkemia Battery Forum](#) by Polito in March 2023
2. [Lithium-ion solid state batteries seminar](#) by FEV in April 2023
3. [International Vienna Symposium](#) by FEV in April 2023
4. [AutomotiveLab Plug 2023](#) by Polito in May 2023
5. [SIA Powertrain](#) show by FEV in June 2023.

12.7 Clustering

NEXTCELL has already identified related initiatives with whom it is expected to start collaboration soon to look for synergies among them.

Apart from the formerly projects included during the proposal preparation, NEXTCELL has also highlighted the projects under the same call, summarising the most important ones in a dedicated section on its [website](#).

Image 11 Related initiatives section on NEXTCELL's website

CoFBAT is a strategic project in achieving the EU energy transition targets through the development of an innovative battery storage solution. Therefore, CoFBAT project aims to develop the next level of battery storage with a modular technology, suitable for different applications that can meet the need for decentralised energy production and supply for private households and industrial robotised devices.

3beLIEve aims to strengthen the position of the European battery and automotive industry in the future xEV market by delivering the next generation of battery cells, designed and made in Europe, for the electrified vehicles market of 2025 and beyond.

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

13. Impact on media outlets and other relevant websites

BATTERIES NEWS

<https://batteriesnews.com/sustainable-innovations-universitat-politecnica-de-valencia-and-cic-energigune-partners-of-nextcell-a-project-that-will-provide-the-next-generation-of-high-performance-lithium-ion-battery-cells/>

CIC ENERGIGUNE

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cic-energigune-brta_revista-energaeda-proyectoseuropeos-activity-7031236845199876096-f155?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

<https://cicenergigune.com/en/news/gelled-cells-next-generation-lithium-ion-batteries-nextcell-cicenergigune>

<https://cicenergigune.com/es/noticias/celdas-gelificadas-proxima-generacion-baterias-ion-litio-nextcell-cicenergigune>

<https://cicenergigune.com/eu/berriak/ion-litiozko-bateriak-gelifikatutako-gelaxka-nextcell-cicenergigune>

DEIA

<https://www.deia.eus/economia/2023/01/11/cic-energigune-avanza-diseno-baterias-6341021.html>

ELECTRIVE

<https://www.electrive.net/2023/01/11/nextcell-forschungsprojekt-zu-gelierten-batteriezellen/>

ELECTRIC VEHICLES MAGAZINE

<https://www.ev-magazine.com/project-that-will-provide-the-next-generation-of-high-performance-lithium-ion-battery-cells/>

ENERGÉTICA XXI

https://energetica21.com/revistas-digitales/enero-febrero-2023_pagina_92

<https://energetica21.com/noticia/cic-energigune-trabaja-en-celdas-basadas-en-el-sistema-de-gelificacion-del-electrolito>

ENERGÍAS RENOVABLES

<https://www.energias-renovables.com/almacenamiento/nextcell-la-proxima-generacion-de-baterias-de-20230110>

EV MAGZ

<https://evmagz.com/nextcell-to-develop-semi-solid-state-batteries-with-gel-inside/>

FORO COCHES ELÉCRICOS

<https://forococheselectricos.com/2023/01/baterias-nextcell-celda-gelificada-economicas-seguras-sostenibles.html>

HÍBRIDOS Y ELÉCTRICOS

https://www.hibridosyelectricos.com/coches/electrodos-electrolitos-gelificados-tecnologia-baterias-semisolidas-espanola_67036_102.html

INTEREMPRESAS

<https://www.interempresas.net/Energia/Articulos/463322-proyecto-Nextcell-trabaja-diseno-celdas-gelificadas-baterias-ion-litio-alto-rendimiento.html>

MOBILIZE FINANCIAL SERVICES

https://twitter.com/Mobilize_FS/status/1615974914741108736

ONDA VASCA

<https://www.ondavasca.com/avance-en-el-diseno-de-baterias-en-euskadi/>

PARKE.EUS

<https://parke.eus/es/cic-energigune-avanza-en-el-diseno-de-celdas-gelificadas-para-la-proxima-generacion-de-baterias-de-ion-litio-de-alto-rendimiento/>

SMARTGRID INFO

<https://www.smartgridsinfo.es/2023/01/12/cic-energigune-investiga-diseno-celda-bateria-aplicando-sistema-gelificacion-electrolito>

SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS

<https://sustainableinnovations.eu/sustainable-innovations-gellified-cell-ion-lithium-batteries-electric-vehicle/>

<https://sustainableinnovations.eu/es/sustainable-innovations-celda-gelificada-baterias-ion-litio-coche-electrico/>

TOP CAR NEWS

<https://es.topcarnews.net/3-entidades-espanolas-desarrollan-las-baterias-nextcell-de-celda-gelificada-mas-economicas-seguras-y-sostenibles-v12857.html>

UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA

<https://www.fs.uni-lj.si/en/press-releases/development-of-advanced-next-generation-solid-state-batteries/>

Funded by the EU. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) Neither the EU nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

[@nextcellproject](https://twitter.com/nextcellproject)
www.nextcell.eu